

FACTORS EFFECTING E-SHOPPING

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Abstract:

Now a days, Internet is altering the way and the manner, consumers shop and purchase products i.e. goods and services and is rapidly evolving into a global phenomenon. With the emergence of WWW (World Wide Web), the merchants have started to sell out their products to those individuals who browse the internet. Consumers can visit the online stores from the comforts of their homes or from any other convenient place and can shop as and when they sit in front of the computer. Many of the experts have optimistic viewpoint regarding the future prospects of online shopping business. The present study has made an attempt to find out the determinant factors as regard to online shopping decisions. For this, a sample of 100 respondents from district Rohtak was taken on the basis of random sampling method. The statistical technique- Weighted Average Score has been used to analyze the data.

Key Words: Online Shopping, Internet Technology, Online Shoppers

Introduction:

With the emergence of WWW (World Wide Web), the merchants have started to sell out their products to those individuals who browse the internet. Consumers can visit the online stores from the comforts of their homes or from any other convenient place and can shop as and when they sit in front of the computer. Consumers can purchase a wide range of products from online stores. In fact, consumers can buy just about anything from web retailers that sell their products over the internet. Books, clothing, toys, software, hardware, household appliances and health products etc., are just some of the hundred of products that consumers can purchase from the online stores. Online shopping allows consumers to browse the internet as and when they are free and even offers those products which are not available in the local stores. In it, Consumers can search the products in multiple online stores at the same time, comparing the quality of material, sizes and the prices of products side by side.

Online Shopping is the process of buying goods and services from those merchants who sell over the internet. It is one of the kind of Electronic commerce whereby customers can directly make the purchase of products i.e. goods and services from a merchant over the internet without any requirement of the intermediary services, by using the web browser. Michael Aldrich is the person who invented the online shopping in 1979. Online shopping is also known by alternative names such as: e-shopping, internet shopping, web shopping, virtual shopping, online store shopping, etc. The largest of these online retailing corporations are: Flipkart, Amazon, Homeshop18 etc. The internet shopping is developing rapidly since last two decades. Information technology has also been developed worldwide. After the development of internet on such a vast scale, the number of web users has also increased and also high speed internet connections, firms thought of using this web development for promoting the sales of their products. Development of information technology also attracts more and more people to change their way of shopping from the traditional mode to the online shopping.

Objective of the Study:

The objective of the present study is to identify the factors that are considered the most while making decision regarding the online purchase of products.

Research Methodology:

Research Design	:	Descriptive
Sources of Data	:	Primary & Secondary
Approach followed in Research	:	Survey Method
Instrument of Research	:	Questionnaire
Types of Research Questions	:	Close Ended
Size of Sample	:	One Hundred Respondents

Scope of the Study:

The present study is basically related to the identification of the factors that are considered by the individuals before making decision regarding the online purchase. The study is conducted among the respondents of Rohtak city. The respondents approached are students, job holders, persons from business class, housewives etc.

Table 1: Factor considered the Most while making decision of Online Shopping

S.No	Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Price Comparison	9	9%
2	Convenience	26	26%
3	Wider Choice	21	21%
4	Trustworthiness of Retailer	12	12%
5	Friend/Relative Referral	3	3%
6	Privacy	1	1%
7	Website Quality	19	19%
8	Security of Payment	3	3%
9	Others	6	6%
10	Total	100	100.00

Source: Researcher's Manual Calculation

Figure 1: Factor considered the Most while making decision of Online Shopping

From the table it is clear that 9 respondents (9%) considers the price factor the most while shopping online, 26 respondents (26%) considers convenience level to be the most important factor while shopping online, 21 respondents (21%) considers the wider choice the most while shopping online, 12 respondents (12%) consider the trustworthiness of retailer as the most important factor, 3 respondents (3%) consider the friend/relative referral to be most important factor while making online shopping decision, only 1 respondent (1%) consider their privacy to be the most important factor, 19 respondents (19%) consider the website quality while making online shopping and only 3 respondents (3%) consider the payment security as the factor influencing their decision the most and 6 respondents (6%) considers the other factors as the influencing factor in online buying decision.

Ranking of the Determinants as Regards to Online Shopping Decisions:

(Where 1 is least important and 5 is most important)

Table 2: Availability of Wider Choice

Rating	1	2	3	4	5
No. of Respondents	6	9	19	22	44

Source: Researcher's Manual Calculation

Weighted Average Score = $(6*1+9*2+19*3+22*4+44*5)/100 = 389/100 = 3.89$

Table 3: Convenience

Rating	1	2	3	4	5
No. of Respondents	4	12	16	20	48

Source: Researcher's Manual Calculation

Weighted Average Score = $(4*1+12*2+16*3+20*4+48*5)/100 = 396/100 = 3.96$

Table 4: Mode of Payment

Rating	1	2	3	4	5
No. of Respondents	8	11	15	24	42

Source: Researcher's Manual Calculation

Weighted Average Score = $(8*1+11*2+15*3+24*4+42*5)/100 = 381/100 = 3.81$

Table 5: Website Quality

Rating	1	2	3	4	5
No. of Respondents	10	14	16	20	40

Source: Researcher's Manual Calculation

Weighted Average Score = $(10*1+14*2+16*3+20*4+40*5)/100 = 366/100 = 3.66$

Table 6: Availability of Information about Products

Rating	1	2	3	4	5
No. of Respondents	8	17	19	22	34

Source: Researcher's Manual Calculation

Weighted Average Score = $(8*1+17*2+19*3+22*4+34*5)/100 = 357/100 = 3.57$

Table 7: Competitive Prices

Rating	1	2	3	4	5
No. of Respondents	8	14	18	27	33

Source: Researcher's Manual Calculation

Weighted Average Score = $(8*1+14*2+18*3+27*4+33*5)/100 = 363/100 = 3.63$

Table 8: Trustworthiness of Retailer

Rating	1	2	3	4	5
No. of Respondents	7	18	20	26	29

Source: Researcher's Manual Calculation

Weighted Average Score = $(7*1+18*2+20*3+26*4+29*5)/100 = 352/100 = 3.52$

Table 9: Factors affecting the decision regarding Online Shopping (with Weighted Average Score)

S.No	Factors Affecting Decision Regarding Online Shopping	Total Score	Weighted Average Score
1	Website Quality	366	3.66
2	Convenience	396	3.96
3	Wider Choice	389	3.89
4	Mode of Payment	381	3.81
5	Information about Products	357	3.57
6	Price Comparison	363	3.63
7	Trustworthiness of Retailer	352	3.52

Source: Researcher's Manual Calculation

Figure 2: Factors affecting the decision regarding Online Shopping (with Weighted Average Score)

It is clear from the table that Highest weighted average score of 3.96 (total score 396) has been attained by Convenience factor, so it is the first most important factor affecting the decision regarding Online Shopping. The second factor affecting decision regarding online shopping is Wider Choice, having Weighted average score of 3.89 (total score 389). The third most considered factor is Mode of Payment, having weighted average score of 3.81 (total score 381). The fourth most considered factor is Website Quality, having weighted average score of 3.66 (total score 366). The fifth most considered factor is price comparisons available, having weighted average score of 3.63 (total score 363). The next considered factor is Availability of Information with regard to the products to be purchased, having weighted average score of 3.57 (total score 357). The next considered factor is Trustworthiness of retailer, having weighted average score of 3.52 (total score 352). Hence it is clear from the table that decision of consumers regarding online shopping is most affected by the factor of convenience, followed by wider choice as the second most important factor, considered during online shopping.

Table 10: Factor Affecting Most the Decision Regarding Online Shopping (with Ranks)

S.No	Factors	Rank
1	Website Quality	IV
2	Convenience	I
3	Wider Choice	II
4	Mode of Payment	III
5	Information about Products	VI
6	Price Comparison	V
7	Trustworthiness of Retailer	VII

Source: Researcher's Manual Calculation

Conclusion:

Above table shows the ranks of various factors affecting brand loyalty of customers. It is clear from the table that first rank (total score 496) has been attained by Convenience so it is the first factor affecting the decision of customers regarding online shopping. Second rank (total score 389) has been attained by wider choice so it is the second factor affecting the decision of customers regarding online shopping. Third rank (total score 381) has been attained by Mode of payment so it is the third factor affecting the decision of customers regarding online shopping. Fourth rank (total score 366) has been attained by Website quality so it is the fourth factor affecting the decision of customers regarding online shopping. Fifth rank (total score 363) has been attained by Price comparisons available so it is the fifth factor affecting the decision of customers regarding online shopping. Sixth rank (total score 357) has been attained by availability of Information regarding products so it is the sixth factor affecting the decision of customers regarding online shopping. Seventh rank (total score 352) has been attained by Trustworthiness of retailer so it is the seventh factor affecting the decision of customers regarding online shopping. Hence, it can be concluded from the table that out of the selected factors, the decision of consumers is highly affected by the Convenience in purchasing the products and least affected by trustworthiness of retailer.

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